

Abstract

This preprint has been submitted to the *The Czech Historical Review* in June 2026. Please note, this preprint has not yet undergone the peer-review process. The final published version of this article may, therefore, have different content. Please feel free to contact the author, your feedback is mostly welcomed. This article examines representations of Muscovy that circulated in the Bohemian lands at the turn of the 16th and 17th centuries. It highlights shifts in the discourse on the tyranny of the tsars, which was significantly influenced by Wittenberg and, subsequently, by Protestant concepts more broadly, including eschatology and medicine. In the Bohemian context, this discourse primarily emerged in cheap prints and histories of Ivan IV. Using Georg Tectander's *Iter Persicum* as an example, the author illustrates a shift towards a more ambivalent portrayal of Muscovy, linked to diplomatic negotiations. Concurrently, this diplomatic report enables us to trace the fundamental elements of the anti-Muscovite discourse that would become influential in the following years, in terms of both religious and cultural criticism. The study compares these representations with contemporary stereotypes of the non-European Other, particularly with regard to the Middle East and the New World.

Keywords: Muscovy, Historiography, Political Writing, Travel Literature, Tyranny, Reformation

Between Tyrannical Despotism and Diplomatic Reality: Knowledge of Muscovy in the Bohemian Lands around 1600

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Many years ago, when first studying texts arising from a fascinating scholarly dispute among Prague University professors upon the origins of the Bohemians, I was prompted to speculate upon the perceptions of Muscovy (i.e., the Grand Duchy of Moscow) and its inhabitants

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prevalent in Bohemia prior to the Thirty Years' War. The controversy in question first emerged following the 1615 publication of Ioannes Matthias' *De origine Bohemorum et Slavorum*, a work in which the Professor of Law at Prague University set out his views on the subject.² In this treatise, Matthias sought to delineate the Migration Period by drawing upon the works of late classical authors and, in a pioneering manner, situate the original territories and migratory patterns of the Bohemians within this historical framework. Contrary to the prevailing Czech historiography of the time, which placed the Slavs' territory in Illyria or Croatia, he instead located their territory in Sarmatia or, as he called it, "Roxolania".

The majority of Bohemian scholars at the time firmly rejected Matthias' interpretation, an attitude possibly connected to the then widespread idea of the "barbaric" forms of government, society and culture in Russian-speaking areas. In opposition to the hypothesis proposed by Matthias, Nicolaus Troilus, who at the time occupied the position of Dean of the Faculty of Arts, advanced an alternative argument. Troilus contended that affection for one's homeland was incongruent with the notion that the Bohemians might be descended from Scythian and Roxolanian barbarians. In the course of a dispute with Matthias, Troilus attributed to him the purported barbaric characteristics of the Scythians and Roxolani. "Let the man who does not want to be Czech remain a Roxolanus. Let the man who considers his ancestors barbarians remain a Scythian and a barbarian," he writes.³ Furthermore, Troilus was the first to identify "Roxolania" with Russia and Muscovy.

Its image was clearly negative in this dispute. I shall show the specific elements constituting the period's knowledge and with what readers in Bohemia could associate them. The lack of research on this topic is surprising, especially given that we know, for example, that in Germany a considerable number of texts about Muscovy were produced from the beginning of the Reformation. German Protestant authors also often drew parallels between the motif of the Turks and Muscovites as God's punishment for sins and the impending end of the world; both nations were referred to, for example, as the armies of Gog and Magog mentioned in Ezekiel's prophecy.⁴ It is very likely that cheap prints published in Bohemia, which have not survived to this day, had the same view of the Muscovites as divine punishment. Their titles would correspond to *Noviny hrozné, strašlivé i žalostivé* (Terrible, Frightful and Lamentable News) from 1563 described the devastating invasion of Lithuania by Muscovite troops; and the following year the same printer, Sebastian Oks of Koloves, published another report on the course of the Livonian War between Ivan the Terrible and Sigismund II Augustus. Another non-extant cheap print was published in 1579 on the Polish-

² See Lucie STORCHOVÁ, *A Late Humanist Treatise on the Origin of the Bohemians, the Academic Polemics and Their Potential to Perform the Other: De origine Bohemorum et Slavorum by Johannes Matthias a Sudetis*, *Acta Comeniana* 22–23, 2009, pp. 152–156; EADEM, *Labia tua maledicentiae et calumniae igne calent: Humanist Polemics and Invectives at the University of Prague from 1610 to 1620*, *Acta Comeniana* 36, 2022, pp. 57–103.

³ *Sermo M. Nicolai Troili Hagiochorani ... de Bohemia pia contra Roxolanos* (Prague 1615), fol. B2b: "Maneat Roxolanus, qui Czechus aut Bohemus esse non vult. Maneat Scythia et barbarus, qui suos veteres pro barbaris agnoscit."

⁴ Thomas KAUFMANN, 1600 – Deutung der Jahrhundertswende im deutschen Luthertum, in: Manfred Jakubowski-Tiessen et al. (eds.), *Jahrhundertwenden. Endzeit- und Zukunftsvorstellungen vom 15. bis zum 20. Jahrhundert*, Göttingen 1999, p. 92; Ken KURIHARA, *Celestial Wonders in Reformation Germany*, London 2014, p. 31.

Russian War.⁵ Andreas Kappeler noted a similar interest in the wars of Ivan the Terrible in cheap prints published mainly in German.⁶

A complex discourse about “Others” and “us” developed after the mid-16th century, promoting religious and civilizational criticism of Muscovites and influencing the cultural identities of the time. Research conducted over the last two decades concerning early modern portrayals of the Turks and inhabitants of the Islamic Near East has provided methodological inspiration. In the case of the Muslim “Other”, attention has been paid by historians such as Laura Lisy-Wagner to the question of how such images co-created the emerging national identity of the local Czech-speaking population.⁷ In the Czech research, more attention has been given to the ways in which the imagined geography of the Islamic Orient, as depicted in travel accounts of the Holy Land and Egypt, contributed to the formation of stereotypes of the “internal enemies” of Bohemian society and the repressive policies enacted against them. This development drew on both biblical imagery and the early Orientalist approach.⁸

The Bohemian sources of knowledge on the Muscovites have not yet been fully mapped. Fragmentary information about Muscovy became available in Czech from the mid-16th century, consisting of cheap prints, historical and astronomical calendars, chronicles, cosmographies, and encyclopaedic handbooks, such as translations of the works of Sebastian Münster and Johannes Böhm Aubanus. In this article, however, I focus on texts which aimed to provide as comprehensive a picture of Muscovy as possible. As we shall see, they reflected the scholarly discussions and globally circulating knowledge of the time, adapting it to the specific cultural environment of Bohemia.

Tyrannical rule in *Kronika mozkevská* (1589)

The first comprehensive portrayal of the “Russian or Muscovite nation” (*národ ruský aneb moskevský*)⁹ in Czech was the extensive *Kronika mozkevská* (1590, 2nd ed. 1602). It is a translation of Alexander Guagnini’s *Sarmatae Europae descriptio*, the first edition of which appeared in Cracow in 1578, supplemented by extracts from Siegmund von Herberstein’s travelogue describing his diplomatic journeys to Moscow in 1516 and 1526/27.¹⁰ It was

⁵ See *Knihopis* K06437, K18854, K06263.

⁶ Andreas KAPPELER, *Ivan Groznyj im Spiegel der ausländischen Druckschriften seiner Zeit. Ein Beitrag zur Geschichte des westlichen Russlandbildes*, Bern 1972, pp. 201–209.

⁷ Laura LISY-WAGNER, *Islam, Christianity and the Making of Czech Identity 1453–1683*, Aldershot 2013.

⁸ Lucie STORCHOVÁ, *Die Konstruktion des orientalischen Körpers in dem Reisebericht Cesta z království českého (1608) von Kryštof Harant z Polžic a Bezdržic*, in: Johanna Holaubek, Hana Navrátilová, Wolf B. Oerter (eds.), *Egypt and Austria II*, Prague 2006, 137–150; EADEM, *Orientalische Gegenwelten? Zur Alteritätskonstruktion des Nahen und „Fernerer“ Ostens in böhmischen Reiseberichten der Frühen Neuzeit*, in: Johanna Holaubek, Hana Navrátilová, Wolf B. Oerter (eds.), *Egypt and Austria III*, Prague 2007, 237–247; EADEM, *Biblische Topographie versus frühneuzeitlichen Orientalismus? Konstruktionen der orientalischen Alterität in böhmischen späthumanistischen Reiseberichten*, in: Johanna Holaubek, Hana Navrátilová, Wolf B. Oerter (eds.), *Egypt and Austria IV*, Prague 2008, 185–214.

⁹ *Kronika mozkevská* (Prague 1590), unnumbered preface, p. 3. In his translation, Hosius referred to the inhabitants of that region as “Muscovites” (*Moskvané*) and “Russians” (*Rusákové, Rusové*).

¹⁰ For further details on Herberstein’s treatise see Marshall T. POE, “*A People Born to Slavery*”: *Russia in Early Modern European Ethnography, 1476–1748*, Ithaca 2000, pp. 117–144; Stéphane MUND, *Orbis Russiarum : genèse et développement de la représentation du monde « russe » en Occident à la Renaissance*, Genève 2003; A. Хорошкевич, *Герберштейн о России*, in: Юст Ругел (ed.), *Герберштейн и его «Записки о Московии»*, Saint Petersburg 2010, pp. 127–177; Tilman G. MORITZ, *Autobiographik als ritterschafiliche Selbstverständigung. Ulrich von Hutten, Götz von Berlichingen, Sigmund von Herberstein*, Göttingen 2019, pp. 141–196; Stefan KARNER, *Zu den Anfängen österreichisch-russischer Beziehungen. Herbersteins Gesandtschaft und sein Bild von Russland*, in: Stefan Karner, Barbara Stelzl-Marx (eds.), *Sigmund von Herberstein. Moscovia:*

published by Daniel Adam of Veleslavín, the most renowned Prague printer at that time, and translated by his colleague Matouš Hosijs, who died during the typesetting. In general, translations produced by Adam's printing house were not simply transfers of text from one language to another. Rather, they were complex cultural translations, with Adam and his collaborators using their sources in a highly creative manner and adapting them to the cultural expectations of their intended Czech readership. According to Josef Macůrek, *Kronika mozkevska* was very well received and swiftly established itself for Czech-speakers as the primary source of information on Muscovy and the regions under its control.¹¹

The book offered Czech readers a relatively broad scholarly discourse and presented portrayals of the Muscovites' supposed barbarism, social disorder, everyday violence, and above all the despotism of the tsars. It is precisely this tyrannical rule and Ivan IV's specific "cruel deeds" that represented the main interpretative framework for understanding the Muscovite state and society. In the preface, Adam draws attention to the category of tyranny. According to him, Grand princes of Moscow ruled "un-Christianly, unduly, inhumanely and extremely cruelly". Ivan IV's tyranny is not only "unheard of," but also "more diabolical than human."¹² Despite such a strong negative assessment, in his preface Adam does not deny the connection between the inhabitants of Bohemia and Muscovy: "Since Muscovites and Russians originate from the same Sarmatian nation as we Czechs, and speak the same language as we and other Slavic nations, albeit with some differences, as do the Poles, Croats, Slovaks, Serbs, etc., it is useful for us Czechs to know and understand how far their nation has spread ... and that it covers nearly half of two continents."¹³

Adam chose Guagnini's *Moscoviae descriptio* precisely because, in addition to the introductory chapters on the regions subordinate to the tsars, which are relatively neutral,¹⁴ it deals with tyrannical rule in great detail and with great suggestiveness.¹⁵ *Moscoviae descriptio* was a suitable source for this purpose because it contained a wealth of information and at the same time offered an extremely critical interpretation of Ivan the Terrible's reign.¹⁶ Even in the preface, Adam suggests how one should interpret Ivan's story: his terrible deeds and tyranny are God's punishment, and Bohemians should be grateful for good governance and social order in their own country. In his words, "All these things are here to teach us, that – knowing that an evil and tyrannical sovereign is given by God to punish a wicked and ungrateful people – we should be grateful for a good and gracious Christian sovereign, who

Die Reisen nach Moskau. Bedeutung und Erbe, Graz 2021, pp. 23–40; Oleg KUDRJAČEV, *Stereotypen über Russland und die Russen. Herbersteins „Rerum Moscoviticarum Commentarii“*, in: *ibid.*, pp. 153–171.

¹¹ Josef MACŮREK, *První český obraz Rusi „Kronika moskevská“ (z r. 1590) a jeho prameny*, *Slavia* 31, 1962, pp. 378–379.

¹² *Kronika mozkevska*, unnumbered preface, p. 4.

¹³ *Ibid.*, pp. 5–6: "poněvadž Moskvané a Rusové pošli jsou z téhož národu sarmatského, jako i my Čechové, a téhož jazyka, kteréhož my a jiní národové slovanští, ač nemálo rozdílněji, jako i Poláci, Charváti, Slováci, Srbi etc. požívají, užitečné jest Čechům našim znáti a věděti, jak daleko jest rozšířený národ jejich a že ... takměř polovici dvou dílů světa *Asiae* a *Europae* obsáhl a naplnil."

¹⁴ Exceptions include shorter passages about unscrupulous merchants or excessive drinking, which leads to violence (*Kronika mozkevska*, p. 4). Bohemian authors generally had little understanding of what we might call the ritual and political functions of alcohol consumption in Muscovy. See Nikolaos CHRISSIDIS, *Whoever does not drink to the end, he wishes evil: Ritual Drinking and Politics in Early Modern Russia*, in: Valerie Kivelson et al. (eds.), *The New Muscovite Cultural History: A Collection in Honor of Daniel B. Rowland*, Bloomington 2009, pp. 107–124.

¹⁵ *Kronika mozkevska*, pp. 152–287.

¹⁶ In the chapter *De tyrannide*, for example, Guagnini used Albert Schlichting's Latin account as his main source, which was popular at the time precisely because it was so terrifying. J. MACŮREK, *První český obraz*, p. 397.

was given to us by God to keep a protective hand over us, over justice, order, and law; so that we can lead a comfortable and peaceful life in piety, continually praying for such a good monarch.”¹⁷

Earlier scholarship viewed the translation of *Sarmatiae Europae descriptio* as a critique of emerging Habsburg absolutism;¹⁸ it also emphasised Adam’s emotional connection to other Slavic nations, as referenced in the aforementioned passage from the preface.¹⁹ However, as demonstrated elsewhere,²⁰ this imagery was based much more on conservative ideas about the social and political order, and how to maintain it in Bohemia, based on proper sovereign–subject relations. In this regard, it builds upon discussions among Czech scholars influenced by their studies at the University of Wittenberg. This tradition also shaped other publishing projects originating from Adam’s printing house. Moreover, a distinctive eschatological interpretation is also evident here. According to Adam, Bohemians should also be grateful to God for protecting them from nations such as the Tartars, Turks and Russians. He concludes this reflection by referencing Psalm 120 and stating that the enemies mentioned therein, the Mesheks and the Kedars, foreshadow the Turks and the Muscovites. He claims that their violent activity is increasing “in these last days of the church of God” (*v posledních těchto časích církve Boží*), i.e. as the world approaches its end.

In particular, the third book of the chronicle draws attention to tyrannical rule. The tsar is the sole sovereign ruler, controlled and restricted by no one; his actions are considered to be the result not of his own will, but of God’s will.²¹ Everyone praises his decision, even if “the grand prince did something shameful and villainous to the detriment of the whole state.”²² The tsar has complete discretion over the lives of his subjects, whether secular or clergy.²³ All material and immaterial goods belong directly to the tsar, including those of the nobility and the Church.²⁴ He collects exorbitant taxes and forcibly takes large sums of money not only from the aristocratic elites but also from people who have earned it through trade or other work.²⁵

The tsar himself selects and appoints all officials, including judges, city administrators and even Church dignitaries such as abbots and bishops. Thus, ecclesiastical and secular administration are not separate in Muscovy.²⁶ Absolute power is therefore also evident in the

¹⁷ *Kronika mozkevská*, unnumbered preface, p. 13. “Což vše k tomu nám sloužití má, aby chom znajíce, že zlá a tyranská vrchnost dává se od Boha k trestání lidu nešlechtného a dobrodiní božských nevděčného, děkovali mu za vrchnost křesťanskú, milostivou a dobrou, kterouž nám dávati ráčí, aby nad námi, nad spravedlností, řádem a právem ochrannou ruku držela a za ni se modlili ustavičně, vedouce život pohodlný a pokojný, ve vši pobožnosti.”

¹⁸ *Lexikon české literatury. Osobnosti, díla, instituce*, vol. 2, Prague 1993, p. 307.

¹⁹ J. MACŮREK, *První český obraz*, p. 404.

²⁰ L. STORCHOVÁ, *Orientalische Gegenwelten*, pp. 246–247; EADEM, *Řád přírody, řád společnosti. Adaptace melanchthonismu v českých zemích v polovině 16. století*, Prague 2021, pp. 309–310.

²¹ *Kronika mozkevská*, p. 158. The Bohemian authors conceptualised the tsars’ power as if it were the unlimited rule of a single person; they paid no attention to complex power relations in the Muscovite court. For more on this, see Sergei BOGATYREV, *The Sovereign and his Counsellors: Ritualised Consultations in Muscovite Culture, 1350s–1570s*, Helsinki 2000.

²² *Kronika mozkevská*, p. 159: “co hanebného a lotrovského kníže na zkázu vši obce učinil.”

²³ *Kronika mozkevská*, p. 157. It was precisely the issue of absolute power, servitude, and enserfment that was also developed in other European countries as a key theme in relation to Muscovy, as demonstrated, for example, by John Michael ARCHER, *Old Worlds: Egypt, Southwest Asia, India, and Russia in early modern English writing*, Stanford 2001, pp. 101–138.

²⁴ *Kronika mozkevská*, p. 136

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 137.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 159–160

judiciary. Instead of “justice and law,”²⁷ he hands out sentences without investigation or trial. The tsar judges all groups of the population directly; the nobility does not intervene in judicial and criminal practice.²⁸ Moreover, when passing judgment, he does not seek the truth, but listens to false testimonies and accusations.²⁹

As Hosius translates, Muscovite society is characterized by complex and violent subordination to the ruler: “All, regardless of profession or status, even without exception for prominent individuals, are burdened with heavy servitude.”³⁰ The subjects then consider this situation so normal that they have “a greater liking for servitude and slavery than for freedom” and even demand to be treated harshly and violently.³¹ However, the complexity of subjugation does not mean that social distinctions are not clearly visible in society – on the contrary, the differences between the boyars (*zemané*) and serfs are evident, and the tsar,³² among other things, precisely determines how individual groups should dress.³³

Violence is used in the administration of the country and violence is also the main interpretative lens through which the functioning of the Muscovite state and society is explained to Czech readers. In general, the tsar punishes not only all acts of disobedience and financial offences extremely harshly but also hints of criticism or dissent. He also punishes gossip and “secret talk”, listening himself to denunciations from untrustworthy informants such as careerist courtiers.³⁴ His individual acts of violence include the targeted murder of local elites and Church leaders, as well as the killing of prisoners of war and inhabitants of conquered territories. Violence and extreme cruelty are illustrated by stories that Guagnini took from Schlichting and thus occupy a large part of the *Kronika mozkevska*. In general, these chapters describe the creation and development of the Oprichnina, the tsar’s life in Alexandrovskaya Sloboda, and the massacres of boyar families. Specifically, these include the murders of Dmitry Ovchina-Obolensky, Prince of Rostov, and Mikhail Temryukovich Cherkassky, a former favourite who had fallen out of favour; the execution of Prince Osip Shcherbaty and the noble religious thinker Matvei Bashkin, who appears incorrectly in the Czech translation as Teodor; the killing of the Gvozdev-Rostovsky brothers and two princes of the Obolensky and Prozorovsky families; the military commander Pyotr Serebryany-Obolensky, Chancellor Ivan Mikhailovich Viskovaty, and the simultaneously executed state treasurer Nikita Funikov. Included in this series describing the elimination of the boyars, there are also highly emotional accounts of the violence accompanying the conquest of Novgorod, Pskov, Tver, and Narva, as well as the killing of Polish prisoners of war.

The murders are described in great detail and often refer to elements of ritual violence, which in this period were associated with pollution, impure animals, purification and mirror punishments – fire and water appear here in various forms, torture with boiling and ice-cold water, drowning, tearing apart by dogs and bears, evisceration, castration, cutting off tongues, ears, and noses. The victims’ heads are often cut off with an axe before they are chopped into pieces. The tsarevich then allegedly desecrates the corpses by trampling and jumping on

²⁷ Ibid., pp. 263–264.

²⁸ Ibid., p. 145.

²⁹ Ibid., p. 175.

³⁰ Ibid., p. 135: “všichni vesměs jakéhožkoliv povolání a stavu beze všeho ušetření některých přednějších osob těžkou služebností ssouzení jsou.”

³¹ Ibid., p. 160.

³² In translation, the term “tsar” (*čžár*) is used directly in addition to “prince” (*kniže*) and “grand prince” (*veliký kniže*), and the dominion is sometimes called “čžarstvo”.

³³ Ibid., pp. 145, 148.

³⁴ Ibid., p. 137.

them.³⁵ Cruel punishments are not only imposed on the accused: in the case of alleged aristocratic traitors, for example, their entire families are murdered, all their subjects are executed, and their property is completely destroyed. The strongly negative tone of the stories is further exacerbated by the fact that the tsar appears insincere and scheming in the midst of these murders. He pretends to have a positive relationship and then orders the killers to kill the victim or lures the victim to the scene of the murder under the pretext of a reward. In the case of Ovchina-Obolensky, he pretends not to know about his death; or he pretends to live in a monastery while planning the murder of noble families.

Moreover, the tsar is directly involved in these acts of violence. He allegedly devises a new method of painful execution using a wheel and takes pleasure in watching executions and torture.³⁶ He participates in torture when he wants prisoners to confess their possessions and hidden treasures.³⁷ He is also directly involved in the killings. The chronicle describes how the tsar stabs his victims in the heart, slits their throats and cuts off their ears; he also chases them and pierces them with a spear like a hunter pursuing prey.³⁸ The most brutal forms of violence are also directed against completely defenceless people, as shown, for example, in a long and very evocative passage describing innocent mothers with small children being driven into a river full of ice.³⁹ The Tsar also commits acts of sexual violence against the wives of high-ranking noblemen, and other women, with long passages concerning kidnapping, rapes and humiliation through undressing.⁴⁰ The bodies of the dead wives are displayed in their own homes, where their families must look at them every day. The tsar then transgresses the rules of sexual morality by having a same-sex relationship with a “Sodomite youth” (*sodomský mládenec*), a practice also associated with Muslim rulers in the Middle East.⁴¹

Tyrannical rule concerns not only the ruler himself, but also all lords and their relationships with their subjects: it permeates all levels of Muscovite society and is transmitted hierarchically through various social groups. By analogy, it also determines relationships within families, where fathers treat their wives and children in the same way as the tsar treats the nobility and lords treat their subjects. Thus, serfs are completely under the power of their masters and are essentially owned by them, which is referred to by various terms in Czech, such as “veliká služebnost”, “poroba”, “manství” and “rukojemství”. Muscovites are born into this relationship, but even freed serfs voluntarily return to it because they cannot imagine any other social order. Subjects are not permitted to own property or move, and must work six days a week for their lords; craftsmen are obliged to sell their goods at a low price to the authorities.⁴² Subjects also internalise daily violence from the authorities as the norm, or even as proof of favour. As Hosius translates, “They believe that their masters

³⁵ Ibid., p. 285.

³⁶ Ibid., pp. 184–185. Neither the chronicle nor other texts in Czech mention the elaborate system of torture with exactly defined, efficient and rational procedures. See Nancy Shields KOLLMANN, *Crime and Punishment in Early Modern Russia*, New York 2012.

³⁷ *Kronika mozkevská*, pp. 210–211.

³⁸ *Kronika mozkevská*, pp. 179, 187, 189, 203, 252, 271.

³⁹ *Kronika mozkevská*, pp. 234–237.

⁴⁰ Ibid., pp. 192, 194, 239, 272–273.

⁴¹ Ibid., pp. 166–167. See also ARCHER, *Old worlds*, p. 122; STORCHOVÁ, *Biblische Topographie*, pp. 198–99.

⁴² *Kronika mozkevská*, pp. 136–140.

do not like them when they are not beaten often enough, and they consider it a sign of anger and disfavour when masters do not swear at them, force them or beat them.”⁴³

Just as in public spaces, violence is present every day in Muscovite homes and families. Wives have the same status as serfs, enjoy no respect, and have no power; in order to be considered honest, they must remain at home, knit, weave, and generally “perform all domestic work like slaves.”⁴⁴ They also consider beatings and verbal abuse to be a sign of their husband’s love and demand it. Fathers also have absolute rights over the lives of their children; they can, for example, indenture their sons three times, and only after the fourth sale do they lose their rights.⁴⁵ In addition to servile relationships and violence, families are a parallel space for other practices associated with tyranny, namely slander, fraud, and false accusations.⁴⁶

In the translation, there are repeated references to Ivan the Terrible’s uncontrolled outbursts of rage.⁴⁷ These passages may be related to the theory of affections (*affectus*), which was popular in Bohemia from the early 1540s onwards. This was when a large group of students from the University of Wittenberg began returning home. They had all been introduced to Melancthon’s *De anima* at the start of their undergraduate studies. Wittenberg scholars considered the human heart to be the seat of affections, which were believed to have a significant influence on bodily spirits and the functioning of the entire body.⁴⁸ Affections were described as irregular and uncontrolled heart movements that occur in response to perceptions or ideas about objects forming in the brain. These perceptions and ideas are transmitted from the brain to the heart via nerves and spirits.

When this concept is transferred to the sphere of political life, tyranny can be seen as a form of government that also arises from uncontrolled affections, particularly anger. Rather than following reason, which is based on the *notitiae naturales* that God has instilled in human hearts, people are seduced by negative affections. This applies to all people, but rulers in particular can easily disrupt social harmony due to negative affections and, in doing so, bring divine punishment upon themselves. In Wittenberg teaching, it was not only the behaviour of contemporary tyrants that was interpreted through the prism of uncontrolled affections but also the historical record concerning tyranny in classical Greece, and even literary works. For example, Prague University lectures on the Aeneid and the Iliad from the 1540s demonstrate this.⁴⁹ Similar to the tyrants of Greek mythology and Roman history, Ivan the Terrible is described as a ruler who, in fits of rage, commits extreme acts of violence against his subjects. According to Adam, Ivan’s acts even surpass all tyrants “who lived before and after the birth of Christ until these times, such as Nero, Valerian, Dionysius, Decius, Maximinus, Julian, and others like them.”⁵⁰

⁴³ Ibid., p. 140: “za to mají, že se panům svým nelíbí, když jich často, jako sluší, nebíjí a soudí to za znamení hněvu a nepřizně, když jim nelají, nepřimlouvají a netepou.”

⁴⁴ Ibid., p. 141: “všecky práce domovní jako otrokyně vykonávají”.

⁴⁵ Ibid., p. 140.

⁴⁶ Ibid., p. 240.

⁴⁷ Ibid. pp. 186, 194, 195, 228, 232.

⁴⁸ For an explanation of this concept and its reception in Bohemia, with references to extensive research, see most recently, Lucie STORCHOVÁ, *Metaphors of the Human Heart and Their Epistemological Shifts after 1600. A Case Study in Changes in Wittenberg Natural Philosophy and Discourses of Power*, *Filosofický časopis*, Special Issue 1/2025, pp. 88–98.

⁴⁹ STORCHOVÁ, *Řád přírody*, pp. 144–154.

⁵⁰ *Kronika mozkevská*, p. 162: “kteříž před narozením i po narození Kristovu byli až do těchto časů, jako Nerona, Valeriana, Dionysia, Decia, Maximina, Juliana a těm podobné.”

This widely shared image of Muscovite tyrannical rule was probably also reflected in Czech cheap prints after 1600 – the only surviving one, albeit incomplete, no longer concerns eschatological fears and parallels between Muscovites and Turks, but rather issues related to the removal of the tyrant from power and the legitimacy of the new ruler. *Historické a pravdivé vypsání* (A Historical and Truthful Account) published by Kašpar Kargesius in 1606⁵¹ describes the life story of False Tsarevich Dimitry, his return to power and 1605 coronation. The story is set against the broad backdrop of disputes between Muscovy, Poland, and Sweden, and is presented as if False Dmitry were the real son of Ivan the Terrible, who survived an assassination attempt, grew up in secret, converted to Catholicism in exile and, with the help of the Polish king, regained the throne. This cheap print describes how he miraculously won the battle, gained the support of his subjects, and proved himself to be an “honest and noble prince” (*poctivé a šlechetné kníže*).⁵² According to Kargesius, his fate is an unusually telling example of “God’s wonderful goodness and providence” (*předivná dobrota a opatrování boží*)⁵³ as Dimitry succeeded only because he fulfilled God’s will. Even so, the discourse of the tsar as a tyrant (in this case Boris Godunov) is still present, as well as the barbarism and ignorance of the people (*nevědomost a hrubost*), which Dimitry resolves to remedy with Jesuit education. *Historické a pravdivé vypsání* develops the metaphor of light, which Dimitry is preparing to bring into the barbaric darkness and thus “illuminate” the Muscovites.⁵⁴

The basic elements of an anti-Muscovite discourse in Tectander’s *Iter Persicum*

Apart from tyrannical rule, what other discourses were associated with Muscovite society after 1600? In the final part of this article I discuss other fundamental elements of anti-Muscovite discourse using as an example a text relating to the Bohemian lands that has been mostly overlooked until now. This text is of particular interest because it portrays the Muscovites in a relatively positive light. This is Georg Tectander’s bestseller, *Iter Persicum. Kurtze, doch außführliche und warhafftige beschreibung der Persianischen Reiß* (1608, 1609 and 1610), in which he describes his diplomatic missions to Safavid Iran.⁵⁵ Georg Tectander was born in Gabel (today Jablonné v Podještědí) in northern Bohemia in 1581. He studied in Germany before entering the service of Rudolf II. In 1602 he departed for Persia as secretary to István Kakas of Zalonkemeny, a Transylvanian nobleman and accredited envoy who was engaged in negotiations for a military coalition against the Ottomans.⁵⁶ Tectander’s travels took him from Bohemia through the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, western and central Russia, and central Asia, ultimately leading him to Tabriz. He resided in the latter for a period of several months, and following the unexpected death of Kakas in 1603, participated directly in diplomatic negotiations with Safavid Shah ‘Abbās I. He returned to Prague via Moscow in 1605.

⁵¹ Knihopis K16788.

⁵² *Historické a pravdivé vypsání* (Prague, 1606), fol. Bivb.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, fols. Aiiia. Diiib.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, fol. Diiib.

⁵⁵ VD17 23:253397U, VD17 3:601621C. For more on power relations between Iran and Muscovy during this period, see Carl Max KORTEPETER, Complex Goals of the Ottomans, Persians, and Muscovites in the Caucasus, 1578–1640, in: Colin P. Mitchell (ed.), *New Perspectives on Safavid Iran*, Abingdon 2011, pp. 59–83.

⁵⁶ Endre VERESS, *Zalánkemény Kakas István 1558–1603*, Budapest 1905.

The ambivalent portrayal of Moscow is linked to Tectander's account of the diplomatic negotiations in which he was involved as part of the delegation.⁵⁷ The status of the Habsburg diplomats is already being discussed as soon as they cross the border of the Grand Duchy, when the mayor of the border town of Vinsko points out that the delegation does not appear sufficiently important.⁵⁸ However, his doubts disappear the moment the legates are granted permission to enter and receive an official welcome: the horsemen sent by the tsar dismount and bow to them, touching the ground with their right hands.⁵⁹ Their position was further strengthened when they demonstrated their Christian faith and, upon inspection of their luggage, it was revealed that they were carrying gifts.⁶⁰

An important part of the negotiations is that the grand prince and his courtiers were to show respect to the Habsburg diplomats as if they were at least partly "equal partners". During the less than a month Kakas and his entourage spent in Moscow (November 19 to December 7), they allegedly received special treatment. They were given diplomatic, high-quality accommodation at the court, in which "everything was so beautifully cleaned and prepared" (*alles so schön ausgeputzt und zugerichtet gewesen*). The tsar's servants took care of their comfort and safety while keeping an eye on them. The opulence of welcome ceremonies and banquets, which the tsar had arranged at their accommodation, was essential for the recognition of the legate; this is a topic that other diplomats, including Herberstein, apparently touched upon as well. Another sign of recognition was the costly gifts they received before being granted audience, such as nine beautiful, perfectly polished and expensively dressed up horses sent by the grand prince to the Habsburg diplomats to bring them to the palace.⁶¹ In terms of representation, the reception of the Habsburg delegation at court, waiting for the audience and the negotiations with the ruler and his son Fyodor Borisovich, were all pivotal moments for Tectander. The tsar and tsarevich were portrayed positively here, as they fulfilled their ceremonial role during the negotiations, thereby providing recognition and legitimacy to the Habsburg delegation. Tectander therefore admired the signs of majesty of the grand prince and his son, including the throne, clothing, and jewellery. He was impressed by the pomp of the Moscow court, the expensive architecture, and the furnishings and equipment of the palace, including the majestic bell. The environment of the grand prince's court, as described by Tectander, can be considered a specific "contact zone" as per the concept used in other contexts by Mary L. Pratt.⁶² It was a dynamic space of transcultural and often asymmetric encounters, in which diplomats held positions of power

⁵⁷ From earlier research on diplomatic reports, see Lloyd E. BERRY, Robert O. CRUMMEY (eds.), *Rude and Barbarous Kingdom: Russia in the Accounts of Sixteenth-Century English Voyagers*, Madison 1968; Marshall T. POE, *A People Born to Slavery*; Stéphane MUND, *La représentation de la Moscovie à la Renaissance: le regard des voyageurs anglais face à la tradition «continentale»*, *Slavica Gandensia* 29, 2002, pp. 123–135; Stéphane MUND, *La mission diplomatique du père Antonio Possevino (s.j.) chez Ivan le Terrible en 1581-1582 et les premiers écrits jésuites sur la Russie moscovite à la fin du xvie siècle*, *Cahiers du monde russe* 45, 2004, 3, pp. 407–440.

⁵⁸ Georg TECTANDER, *Iter Persicum* (Leipzig 1609), p. 9.

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 13.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, pp. 23–29. The diplomatic gifts reportedly aroused an unhealthy interest among officials ("sie ihren unvesettlichen geitz und begierd der Geschenck nicht konnten verbergen"; p. 29)

⁶¹ *Ibid.* p. 33: "9 schöne Rosse so sehr wohl geputzt... unter deren das eine mit einer köstlichen Satteldeck von rothen Sammet und Gold gesticket/ das zeugt alle mit Silber beschlagen und mit Edelgestein versetzt gewesen...".

⁶² Mary Louise PRATT, *Imperial Eyes: Travel Writing and Transculturation*, London, New York 1992, p. 7.

and received specific recognition and treatment. However, they were separated from the everyday space of the city and its inhabitants and did not move freely within it.

The fact that Tectander could not move freely outside the court does not mean, however, that he did not comment extensively on the city and its inhabitants in his travelogue. On the contrary, *Iter persicum* includes very negative portrayals which he adapted from Guagnini and other authors. The result is thereby somewhat paradoxical because Tectander mixed positive discourses referencing his personal experience with negative intertextual imagination. It is precisely this ambivalence which enables us to analyse the fundamental components of anti-Muscovite discourse in East-Central Europe around 1600. These elements were considered fundamental and were probably so widely shared and expected by readers at the time that Tectander (and perhaps many other authors from a similar cultural background) simply considered it “natural” to mention them in his texts.

This negative imagery is fully developed in the chapters *Descriptio urbis* and *Mores und Sitten*. Tectander describes the city of Moscow in a rather neutral manner, following the standard apodemic structure for observing and describing an early modern city. In the conventional sequence, he mentions the river, ramparts, monasteries, churches and palaces, but combines this with critical passages. According to Tectander, Muscovy is characterised as a barren wilderness full of mud and infertile soil (*ein püschits/ mehren theils wildes wüstes und sümpffichts Land*). It is dark and inhumanly cold and the ground is covered in deep snow (*unmenschliche kälte und tieffer schnee*). In Moscow itself there are poor and unsightly houses built of wood which have neither windows nor chimneys and are not built next to each other to form streets.⁶³

However, the basic elements of anti-Muscovite discourse mainly concerned people. Regardless of their Christian faith, Tectander adopts a clearly more critical attitude toward Muscovites – although he labels Persians as “pagans”, in his eyes they are still better-mannered, indeed, better in every respect than the Muscovites.⁶⁴ Similar to contemporary literature about the Turks and travelogues about the Holy Land, Tectander offers a critical perspective on the religious practices (*ritus*) and everyday life of the inhabitants of Moscow (*vita et mores*).⁶⁵ He pays close attention to what he calls *Graeca fides corrupta*.⁶⁶ Although Muscovites consider themselves to be the most devout Christians, Tectander claims that they are not sufficiently pious and do not even observe the Ten Commandments. They commit various sins, especially of a sexual nature (*Hurerey, Unzucht*). Drawing on his Protestant background, Tectander suggests that the Muscovites are too preoccupied with material objects of devotion, especially jewels, crucifixes and altar images, to which they supposedly behave as if they were living people (*als wen es sie lebendigen personen weren*).⁶⁷ In this sense, they could even be considered secret polytheists, because they worship saints as fervently as if they had multiple gods. Their masses focus too much on the external aspects of the ceremony:

⁶³ *Iter Persicum*, p. 40: “Die Häuser und Gebäuder sind alles mehren theils höltzern / und unformirlich/ nicht wie bey uns nahe bey einander/ und in den Stuben mehren theils mit rauchöfen/ und ohne Glaßfenster erbawet.”

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 107. “Was nun ferner ihre Sitten und Mores betreffen thut/ sind dieselben/ ungeachtet/ dass sie Heyden sein/ viel höfflicher unnd ubertreffen in allen die Moscowiter”.

⁶⁵ Wolfgang NEUBER, *Grade der Fremdheit, Alteritätskonstruktion und experientia-Argumentation in deutschen Turcica der Renaissance*, in: Bodo Guthmüller, Wilhelm Kühlmann (eds.), *Europa und die Türken in der Renaissance*, Tübingen 2000, 249–265, here 254.

⁶⁶ *Iter Persicum*, *ibid.*, p. 44.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 47.

Tectander speaks of juggling and idolatry during services (*Gaukeley und Götzendienste*).⁶⁸ Ordinary believers observe ceremonies and strict fasts but according to Tectander they often do not even know how to pray. Fasts and other ascetic rules are observed with unhealthy strictness in monasteries.⁶⁹ The superficiality of faith and inadequate education is also evident among priests, who are said to have only basic literacy skills and to spend their time singing psalms in churches instead of focusing on preaching, as Protestant pastors do. This prevents them from developing individual piety among the faithful.⁷⁰ Tectander further mentions that Muscovite priests are allowed to marry, which was a topic of debate in Bohemia after 1600. An excessive interest in outward acts of faith that did not reflect individual piety was one of the stereotypes about Islam in Czech travelogues of the time. Tectander draws further parallels between Islam and Orthodox Christianity, for example when he claims that Orthodox churches resemble mosques; they are built “*fast auff die Türkische art*”.⁷¹

When it comes to the functioning of society and everyday life, Tectander also develops a discourse of tyrannical rule, which contrasts sharply with his positive representations of the Court, diplomatic negotiations, and recognition by the monarch. The current tsar, whom he refers to as *Großfürst*, came to power as an autocrat through violence and had his brother-in-law poisoned.⁷² One of the fundamental elements of the anti-Muscovite discourse is the transfer of the model of a single ruler to other social relationships, primarily between the nobility and their subjects, who live as *rechte leibeigene Knechte*.⁷³ As Tectander explains, the situation in Muscovy differs significantly from that in the German lands. The Muscovite nobility are uneducated and treat their subjects extremely harshly and violently. They can restrict or even kill their subjects with impunity.

Husbands and fathers have a similar relationship with their families. Muscovite noblemen separate women in the privacy of their homes, literally like birds in a cage⁷⁴ and do not allow them to be in public or even talk to male guests. Women only meet among themselves, which again draws a parallel with contemporary images of the Islamic Middle East. The lack of freedom within families is further evident in marriage-related practices. Tectander paid attention to this seemingly unimportant issue because the married estate was a fundamental topic in the Lutheran environment, one that had resonated strongly since the mid-16th century, even in Bohemia.⁷⁵ In Muscovite society, marriages were allegedly decided

⁶⁸ Ibid., p. 54.

⁶⁹ Ibid., pp. 51–52.

⁷⁰ Ibid., p. 49: “Ihre Priester und Pfaffen studieren gar nichts/ und seind auch sonst die *studia* bey ihnen gar nicht im brauch/ alß wie bey uns/ sind grobe ungeschickte Leut/ dürffen wol sagen/ daß durch die *studia* bey uns Teutschen/ so viel und mancherley Religionen und Abgötterey herrühren/ und wenn dieselben schreiben und lesen können/ sind sie zu Priestern und weltlichen Regimenten geschickt genugsam./ Es wird bey ihnen gar nichts gepredigt sondern singen und plappern David *Psalterium*/ doch auch verstümmelt/ auff ihre Sprach/ und sonst andere Moscovitterische Gesänge mehr.”

⁷¹ *Iter Persicum*, p. 44. However, during the same period, strong anti-Islamic and anti-Tatar imagery and rhetoric were developing in Russian literature, see Donald OSTROWSKI, *Muscovy and the Mongols: Cross-Cultural Influences on the Steppe Frontier, 1304–1589*, Cambridge 1998; Janet MARTIN, *Religious Ideology and chronicle depictions of Muslims in 16th-century Muscovy*, in: Valerie Kivelson et al. (eds.), *The New Muscovite Cultural History: A Collection in Honor of Daniel B. Rowland*, Bloomington 2009, pp. 285–299.

⁷² *Iter Persicum*, p. 30.

⁷³ Ibid., p. 45.

⁷⁴ Ibid., p. 58.

⁷⁵ From the early stages of the Reformation, the married estate was regarded as the cornerstone of the doctrine of the three estates, and a well-ordered household as a model for the functioning of other social relationships. See Luise SCHORN-SCHÜTTE, *Die Drei-Stände Lehre*, in: Markus Friedrich et al. (eds.), *Perspectum. Ausgewählte*

by the fathers, who arranged marriages for their children aged 9 or 10 based on financial considerations. The children had to obey their fathers and were not yet able to understand the importance of *Ehestand* as a social and religious institution.⁷⁶

Other widely held stereotypes are associated with perceptions of violence and the low level of education among Muscovites. The first of these is rudeness and uncouth behaviour. According to Tectander, for example, Muscovites eat with their hands at mealtimes, as if they were animals.⁷⁷ The ascription of animal-like features to cultural Others was a widespread narrative strategy in the period's Czech travel writing. Kryštof Harant, one of the travellers to the Holy Land, employed figurative language to describe the everyday life, lack of social order and violence of nomadic communities living in the Egyptian desert. He noted that they resembled "dogs" when sitting on the ground and eating with their bare hands, with which they then besmirched themselves.⁷⁸

Everyday violence is then linked to the last discursive element, which is the representation of cannibalism during the great famine in the year that Tectander visited Moscow, 1603. Here, too, the strongly negative images associated with the famine contrast sharply with the previous passages, in which Tectander understood the lavish banquets at the court, which took place at the same time, to be a sign of recognition of the Habsburg diplomats. As Tectander explains, entire villages died out during the famine and terror spread. There was a risk of assault and theft in public spaces. People were forced to eat impure animals (*unreine Thier*), such as cats and dogs.⁷⁹ Above all, cannibalism became widespread, as illustrated by the widespread story of how, during famines, the meat of the dead was chopped up and added to dumplings (*pirogi*).⁸⁰ By around 1600, stories about cannibalism had a broad cultural context in Bohemia. They could refer to depictions of indigenous peoples of the New World, such as the Tupinambá, as presented in the Czech translation of Jean de Léry's *Historia navigationis in Brasiliam* of 1590, or to numerous narratives about sieges, particularly those concerning the siege and destruction of Jerusalem during the First Jewish–Roman War.⁸¹

Conclusion

Leaving aside the internal "Others" in the Czech lands, such as the non-settled population, the Muscovites indeed represented one of the "nearest Others", carrying a number of negative connotations linked to the political and religious discourses of that era. At the same time, however, they were also specifically ambivalent – if only because Muscovites were

Aufsätze zur Frühen Neuzeit und Historiographiegeschichte anlässlich ihres 65. Geburtstages, München 2014, pp. 255–263.

⁷⁶ *Iter Persicum*, p. 57.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*: "auch im Essen und Trincken sind die Moscovitter Viehische grobe Leute und ungeschliffene Leute/ essen gar gemeinlich ohne Teller und Messer/ greiffen mit blossen Fäusten in die Speisen."

⁷⁸ HARANT, *Putování aneb Cesta z království českého do města Benátek, odtud po moři do země Svaté*, Vol. II, Prague 1608, pp. 107–112.

⁷⁹ *Iter Persicum*, p. 42.

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*: "dass in der Stadt zu unterschieden mahlen bey den Beckern Kuchen/ die sie Pirogen nennen/ und fast auff die art wie wir die Pfankuchen bey uns zubacken pflegen/ gekaufft worden sind / daran sie sonst allerley Fleisch zu backen / an stat desselben Menschenfleisch/ und die gestorbenen Menschen gestolen / die zu stücken gehawt/ gefressen/ oder also mit verkauft haben."

⁸¹ See Lucie STORCHOVÁ, *The Jewish War, God's Wrath and 'the Most Unfortunate People': Representations of the Jews and Judaism in Late Sixteenth-Century Protestant Literature in the Bohemian Lands*, *Judaica Bohemiae* 57, 2022, 1, pp. 15–17; Merrall L. PRICE, *Consuming Passions: The Uses of Cannibalism in Late Medieval and Early Modern Europe*, New York, London 2003.

considered a linguistically related group (that is, sharing a Slavic language) and/or because interest in their positive portrayal might have been linked, for example, to the professional self-presentation of the authors and their diplomatic activities in Moscow. However, the mere fact of geographical proximity does not mean that knowledge produced by Bohemian authors primarily expressed their first-hand experience; their imageries were multi-faceted and drew on sophisticated intertextual relations. This applies above all to descriptions of everyday violence in a society defined by a tyrannical system of government. As demonstrated above, tyrannical rule was the primary interpretive framework for Muscovy at the time, a fact that is particularly evident in *Kronika mozkevská* and cheap vernacular prints. Tectander's travelogue thus illustrates a broad sharing of certain thematic units, rather incoherent and fragmentary, which were probably considered so basic that they could have been or even must have been incorporated into a text with a partly positive message. His image of tyrannical rule is therefore actually paradoxical, because it is at one and the same time negative on the basic stereotypical level common to many other works whilst describing diplomatic negotiation based on mutual recognition, thereby implying that the Court had specific legitimacy. Another shared element of texts from the period was that they described tyranny not just as a matter of the ruler's behaviour but as a pattern permeating other power relations in society, including those of the nobility, their subjects and the family. Descriptions of Muscovite tyranny could further be linked to other Protestant discourses, such as medicine, practical theology and eschatology and, after 1600, the question of whether it is legitimate to depose a tyrant and install another ruler. Not surprisingly, many of these themes overlapped with imageries of other places, especially the Islamic Near East as described by Bohemian pilgrims.

Bohemia was, of course, only a relatively small multi-religious, multi-ethnic region which around 1600 possessed limited Latin and vernacular literature; however, interest in this topic was evident, as were the connections to the international scholarly discourse on the Muscovites. Nevertheless, the question remains whether or not this type of knowledge was, to some extent, typical of regions influenced by intellectual Protestantism. In any case, the richness of discourses related to Muscovites in East-Central Europe in general, and the ways in which these images circulated transculturally in particular, are much more complex issues that need to be addressed in future research.